

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION FOR:

Four-compartment Diffusion Model of Cortisol Disposition: Comparison to Three Alternative Models in Current Clinical Use

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A. Terminology: The term **plasma free cortisol** is inclusive and refers to either serum or plasma free cortisol measured in the vascular (plasma) compartment.

Corticosteroid replacement therapy (CRT) treatment effect was defined as the difference in means of specified outcomes (for example 28-day mortality in placebo minus 28-day mortality in the CRT group). *CRT treatment effect size* was defined as the difference in means of specified outcomes for placebo vs. CRT divided by the pooled standard deviation of both groups. Note that for a binomial outcome, such as 28-day mortality, one could compute the standard deviation from the estimated binomial percentages.

Euadrenal was used denote a normality of adrenocortical function in the context of exclusion criteria typically applied in placebo-controlled trials of CRT. The term is also intended to exclude individuals affected by conditions or using medications, such as exogenous corticosteroids (1), that are known to affect HPA function. As used in the term *euadrenal, critical ill patients* (ECI), we consider this population, at least conceptually, to also indicate the absence of measurable clinical or biochemical evidence of adrenal hypofunction prior to the episode of critical illness or subsequent to recovery of usual good health.

Critical illness related corticosteroid insufficiency (CIRCI) was also considered in the context of randomized, placebo-controlled trials in critically ill patients. CIRCI is defined conceptually as the subset of ECI in whom CRT is associated with measurably improved clinical outcomes relative to placebo. This definition excludes the subset of ECI patients in whom CRT is associated with similar or worse clinical outcomes relative to placebo.

B. Cortisol appearance may be expressed in units of concentration/time or mass/time:

The term Z_F refers to cortisol appearance rate in the concentration space (concentration/time, nmol/L/min), whereas the term Z_{QF} refers to cortisol appearance rate in the mass space (mass/time, nmol/min). For model equations formulated in the concentration space (e.g. Eq 1 in manuscript and equations for Models 1-3 in Section D below), both Z_F (Models 2-4) and Z_{ToIF} (Model 1) are expressed in units of concentration/time (nmol/L/min). Our use of the term *cortisol secretion rate* (CSR) refers to the model-specific rate of cortisol appearance in the concentration space (nmol/L/min). Our use of the term CSR does not distinguish adrenal vs. extra-adrenal sources (e.g. thru 11- β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase 1) of cortisol production or appearance (2-4).

Intravenous infusion of ^2H -labeled cortisol (D4-cortisol) at known rates (nmol/min):

In the so-called stable isotope dilution method, cortisol appearance rates are typically expressed in units of mass/time (Z_{QF}). In this context, Z_{QF} may be defined in reference to known rates of D4-cortisol infusion (mass/time) whilst the ratio of unlabeled to labeled X_{ToIF} is treated as a multiplicative factor (also see Supplementary Data, Section V).

Cortisol appearance rates in Model 4 may be alternatively expressed in units of concentration or mass per time: Note that Model 4 may be formulated alternatively in

units of both mass/time (dQ/dt , nmol/min, see Eq 1'-4' in Section G, below) as well as concentration/time (dX_F/dt or dX_{TotF}/dt , nmol/L/min, see Eq 1-4 in manuscript). When Model 4 is formulated in units of mass, the appearance rate of cortisol (Z_{QF}) is expressed in units of mass/time (nmol/min, see Eq 1' in Section G, below) and distributed initially within the vascular volume (V), as shown in Section G below.

C. The term for metabolic elimination of cortisol (α) is contextual to model: The definitions for metabolic elimination of X_{TotF} (Model 1) or X_F (Models 2-4) is specified by the model in which they are applied. That is illustrated by the fact that in single compartment models, α predicts monoexponential decay of X_{TotF} (Model 1) and X_F (Model 2). Log-transformation of cortisol concentrations in these models yields a linear function, as illustrated in Figure 4B (manuscript) and Figure S5 below. Therefore, computational methods are not required to obtain best fit solutions for α and corresponding cortisol half-life (τ) (5-7). While Models 2-3 both model elimination of free cortisol, Model 3 is more complex insofar as it also includes the dynamic, reversible exchange of free cortisol with serum binding proteins, CBG and albumin, which was modeled simply by mass action principles. Model 4 expands upon Model 3 by adding the concept of free cortisol diffusion to and from the extravascular space. Because of the additional equations that account for protein binding and diffusion of free cortisol in Models 3 and 4 (see Eq 1-4 in manuscript), these multicompartments predict a pattern of decay of cortisol concentrations that does not conform to simple, monoexponential elimination. Accordingly, solutions for α_3 and α_4 based upon serial measurements of X_F or X_{TotF} require support of computer resources involving iterative

variation in parameter estimates and simultaneous solution of multiple non-linear differential equations (i.e. numerical methods).

To expand upon this issue, consider a simple differential equation $\frac{dx}{dt} = -\alpha x$ to represent cortisol elimination. The rate of elimination, $\frac{dx}{dt}$, is proportional to the cortisol concentration (x), with α being the constant of proportionality. The solution of this differential equation can have the form $x = Ce^{-\alpha t}$, where C is a constant, namely, the y-intercept at t=0. This solution is an exponential function. Hence, this differential equations for one-compartment Models 1 and 2 describe monoexponential elimination of cortisol using a rate constant (α). Models 3 and 4 include other, simultaneous nonlinear differential equations that do not conform to this simple monoexponential solution. Thus, the values of α_3 and α_4 in Models 3 and 4, respectively, have meanings that are qualitatively and quantitatively different than the simple monoexponential decay described by α_1 and α_2 in the one-compartment models.

D. Differential equations for Models 1-3: Models 1 and 2 treat total (X_{TotF}) and free (X_{F}) cortisol, respectively, as a single compartment in the plasma distribution volume.

Model 1 is formulated as a simple, linear differential equation:

$$\text{Eq. 1) } dX_{\text{TotF}}/dt = -\alpha_1 X_{\text{TotF}} + Z_{\text{TotF}},$$

where X_{TotF} (nmol/L) is the concentration of total cortisol measured in serum or plasma; Z_{TotF} (nmol * L⁻¹ * min⁻¹) is the appearance rate of total cortisol in the concentration space; and α_1 (min⁻¹) is the monoexponential elimination rate constant for X_{TotF} .

Model 2 is also formulated as a simple, linear differential equation, but is based exclusively on concentrations of free cortisol (X_{F}):

$$\text{Eq. 2) } dX_{\text{F}}/dt = -\alpha_2 X_{\text{F}} + Z_{\text{F}},$$

where X_F (nmol/L) is the concentration of free cortisol measured in serum or plasma;
 Z_F (nmol * L⁻¹ * min⁻¹) is the appearance rate of free cortisol in the concentration space;
and α_2 (min⁻¹) is the monoexponential rate constant for elimination of free cortisol from
the plasma compartment.

Model 3 is formulated as three, non-linear differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1'') \quad \frac{dX_F}{dt} &= -\{\alpha + \kappa_1^C (X_{TotCBG} - X_C) + \kappa_1^A (X_{TotA} - X_A)\} * X_F \\
 &\quad + \kappa_{-1}^C * X_C + \kappa_{-1}^A * X_A + Z_F \\
 2'') \quad \frac{dX_C}{dt} &= -\kappa_{-1}^C * X_C + \kappa_1^C (X_{TotCBG} - X_C) * X_F \\
 3'') \quad \frac{dX_A}{dt} &= -\kappa_{-1}^A * X_A + \kappa_1^A (X_{TotA} - X_A) * X_F
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$\frac{dX}{dt}$ = the derivative of a concentration X with respect to time t,

change in concentration per unit time, or rate of change of X,
here in units of nmol/L/min = nM/min;

X_F = the time-varying concentration of plasma free cortisol in the vascular volume (V);

X_C = the time-varying concentration of CBG-bound cortisol in the vascular volume (V);

X_A = the time-varying concentration of albumin-bound cortisol in the vascular volume (V);

X_{TotCBG} = the total CBG concentration equal to the sum of free CBG and cortisol-bound CBG,
such that $X_{TotCBG} = X_{freeCBG} + X_C$, here measured;

X_{TotA} = the total albumin concentration equal to the sum of free and cortisol-bound albumin,
such that $X_{TotA} = X_{freeA} + X_A$, typically measured;

Z_F = the time-varying free cortisol appearance rate in the concentration space (nmol/L/min);

α = the monoexponential term for free cortisol elimination rate (min⁻¹);

κ_1^C = the forward (association) rate constant (on-rate in units of 1/(nM-sec)) and

κ_{-1}^C = the backward (dissociation) rate constant (off-rate in units of 1/sec)

Both for the reversible binding reaction $X_{\text{freeCBG}} + X_F \rightleftharpoons X_{FC}$;

κ_1^A = the forward (association) rate-constant (on-rate in units of 1/(nM-sec)) and

κ_{-1}^A = the backward (dissociation) rate constant (off-rate in units of 1/sec)

Both for the reversible binding reaction $X_{\text{freeA}} + X_F \rightleftharpoons X_{FA}$.

X_{TotF} = the time-varying concentration of total cortisol in the vascular volume (V) equal to the sum of free, CBG-bound, and albumin-bound cortisol concentrations in the vascular volume ($X_{\text{TotF}} = X_F + X_C + X_A$).

Note that X_{TotF} is not explicitly mentioned in Eq 1-3. However, it is typically the measured cortisol concentrations to which models are fit, and may be calculated as the sum of its components, X_F , X_C , and X_A , which are represented in the above equations.

E. Diffusion terms *flux* and *concentration gradient* when barrier area and thickness are

unknown: In the diffusion equation, $dQ_F/dt = k*[X_F - X_{Fe}]$, dQ_F/dt is the rate of change

in cortisol mass in the vascular volume and the permeability constant (k) is proportional

to $D * A/\delta$, where D is the diffusion constant (area/time, cm^2/min), A is the area (cm^2) of

the diffusion barrier, and δ is the thickness of the diffusion barrier (cm). Note that in our

formulation of Model 4, the diffusion coefficient, barrier surface area, and barrier

thickness are expressed as a single, composite parameter, i.e. the permeability constant

(k). Terms for diffusion barrier geometry are not specified by the permeability constant,

which therefore necessitates some adjustment to definitions of *flux* and *concentration*

gradient. For example, as applied in Fick's first law of diffusion, the term *flux* refers to

the rate of cortisol mass/time (dQ/dt) adjusted for surface area (A). However, since A was

not specified in our formulation of Model 4, the term ***cortisol flux*** is also used herein to

include dQ/dt without adjustment for surface area. Similarly, the term *cortisol*

concentration gradient as applied in Fick's first law would refer to the difference

between plasma free and extravascular cortisol concentrations adjusted for barrier width

$(X_F - X_{Fe})/\delta$. However, since δ was not specified in our formulation of Model 4, the term **cortisol concentration gradient** is also used herein to include $(X_F - X_{Fe})$ without adjustment for barrier width (δ).

F. Comparison of HV and CBG-deficient groups: CBG concentrations were significantly reduced ($P < 0.001$) in CBG-deficient subjects (252 ± 24 nmol/L) compared to HV (901 ± 208 nmol/L), as was cortisol binding affinity (see Supplementary Data, Section I).

Height was significantly less ($P = 0.03$) in CBG deficient subjects (156 ± 4.9) relative to HV (171.7 ± 8.4 cm). Body surface area (BSA) was also lower in the CBG-deficient group (1.4 ± 0.01 vs. 1.7 ± 0.2 m², $P = 0.01$), and there was a trend to lower weight in the CBG-deficient group as well (54.5 ± 4.0 vs. 69.8 ± 14.8 kg, $P = 0.06$). Serum albumin concentrations were not measured in Perogamvros *et al* (8). Therefore, we used median albumin concentrations stratified by age and gender to match individual subjects (9).

G. Formulation of Model 4 Equations 1-4 in units of cortisol mass rather than concentration:

$$1') \quad \frac{dQ_F}{dt} = - \left\{ \alpha + \frac{\kappa_1^C}{V} (Q_{TotCBG} - Q_C) + \frac{\kappa_1^A}{V} (Q_{TotA} - Q_A) \right\} * Q_F \\ + \kappa_{-1}^C * Q_C + \kappa_{-1}^A * Q_A - k \left(\frac{Q_F}{V} - \frac{Q_{Fe}}{V_e} \right) + Z_{QF}$$

$$2') \quad \frac{dQ_C}{dt} = - \kappa_{-1}^C * Q_C + \frac{\kappa_1^C}{V} (Q_{TotCBG} - Q_C) * Q_F$$

$$3') \quad \frac{dQ_A}{dt} = - \kappa_{-1}^A * Q_A + \frac{\kappa_1^A}{V} (Q_{TotA} - Q_A) * Q_F$$

$$4') \quad \frac{dQ_{Fe}}{dt} = +k \left(\frac{Q_F}{V} - \frac{Q_{Fe}}{V_e} \right)$$

where

$\frac{dQ}{dt}$ = the derivative of a quantity Q with respect to time t ,
change in quantity per unit time , or rate of change of Q ,

here in units of nmol /min;

Q_F = the time-varying quantity of plasma free cortisol in the vascular volume (V);

Q_C = the time-varying quantity of CBG-bound cortisol in the vascular volume (V);

Q_A = the time-varying quantity of albumin-bound cortisol in the vascular volume (V);

Q_{Fe} = the time-varying quantity of free cortisol in the extravascular volume (V_e);

Q_{TotCBG} = the total CBG quantity equal to the sum of free CBG and cortisol-bound CBG, such that $Q_{TotCBG} = Q_{freeCBG} + Q_C$, here measured;

Q_{TotA} = the total albumin quantity equal to the sum of free and cortisol-bound albumin, such that $Q_{TotA} = Q_{freeA} + Q_A$, typically measured;

Z_{QF} = the time-varying free cortisol appearance rate (nmol /min) in the vascular volume (V);

α = the free cortisol elimination rate constant (min^{-1});

k = the permeability constant in Fick's first law: $\frac{dQ_{Fe}}{dt} = k(X_F - X_{Fe})$;

where $X_F = \frac{Q_F}{V}$ and $X_{Fe} = \frac{Q_{Fe}}{V_e}$ are concentrations (nmol/L) and Q_{Fe} is the quantity (nmol) of free cortisol in the extravascular compartment, and the permeability constant (k) is proportional to $D * A/\delta$, where D is the diffusion constant (area/time, cm^2/min), A is the area (cm^2), and δ is the barrier (membrane) thickness (cm).

κ_1^C / V = the forward (association) rate constant (on-rate in units of $1/(\text{nmol}\cdot\text{sec})$) and

κ_{-1}^C = the backward (dissociation) rate constant (off-rate in units of $1/\text{sec}$)

Both for the reversible binding reaction $X_{freeCBG} + X_F \rightleftharpoons X_{FC}$, where $X = Q/V$ are concentrations.

κ_1^A / V = the forward (association) rate-constant (on-rate in units of $1/(\text{nmol}\cdot\text{sec})$) and

κ_{-1}^A = the backward (dissociation) rate constant (off-rate in units of $1/\text{sec}$)

Both for the reversible binding reaction $X_{freeA} + X_F \rightleftharpoons X_{FA}$, where $X = Q/V$ are concentrations.

Q_{TotF} = the time-varying quantity of total cortisol in the vascular volume (V) equal to the sum of free, CBG-bound, and albumin-bound cortisol quantities in the vascular volume ($Q_{TotF} = Q_F + Q_C + Q_A$).

Note that Q_{TotF} is not in any of Eq 1-4. However, it is typically the measured cortisol quantities to which models are fit, and may be calculated as the sum of its components, Q_F , Q_C , and Q_A , which are represented in the above equations.

Note. These equations can also be converted to other units of quantity such as mg by dividing every Q as well as Z_{QF} and κ_1^C / V and κ_1^A / V by the conversion factor (say, 2759 nmol/mg). Actually, this factor cancels everywhere except for κ_1^C / V and κ_1^A / V .

Numerical methods, initial conditions and parameters solved for Model 4,

calculation of plasma volume, and steady state solutions (Models 1-4): Models 1-4 were separately applied to cortisol-time series data for individual subjects. Parameter solutions for Models 1-4 were optimized iteratively by numerical methods, as previously described (3,4). All numerical procedures were performed in MATLAB programming environment using the MATLAB ODE15s solver. Model 4 has four (4) compartments representing free cortisol (X_F), CBG-bound cortisol (X_C), albumin-bound cortisol (X_A), and extravascular free cortisol (X_{Fe}); see equations 1)-4) in the paper. Model 4 requires simultaneous solution of three unknown parameters: (i) free cortisol elimination rate constant (α_4), (ii) permeability constant (k), and (iii) extravascular volume (V_e) (Table 1). Initial conditions for Model 4 just before $t=0$ is that cortisol concentrations in all four compartments are equal to zero. At $t=0$, solutions were determined empirically as a brief (20 s) infusion of cortisol mass (20 mg = 55,249 nmol) distributed uniformly in the vascular (plasma) volume (V). The cortisol appearance rate (Z_F in Eq 1) was assumed to be zero for Models 1-3. In Model 4, Z_F was considered to be zero after the initial 20-second bolus infusion.

Calculation of plasma volume: Blood volume was calculated per subject according to weight, height, and sex using Nadler's formula (10). The plasma fraction of the blood volume was obtained by correction for hematocrit using normative population values (40% in women and 45% in men).

Steady state was defined in the context of the continuous cortisol infusion experiment, in which cortisol is infused at a constant, known rate (mass/time) and the contributions of endogenous cortisol production are rendered negligible. Steady state is represented as an asymptotic condition at which cortisol concentrations *in all compartments* are approximately constant as a function of time and the mass of cortisol eliminated per minute is constant and equal to the infusion rate (mass/min).

Steady state solutions for Models 1-4: Steady state equations in the continuous hydrocortisone infusion experiment for Models 1-4 were obtained by setting all time derivatives to zero, as previously described (3,11). This yielded a common form for all four models:

$$(5) \quad Z_{FS} = \alpha * F_S,$$

where Z_{FS} is the (constant) rate of cortisol appearance rate at steady state expressed in the concentration space (nmol/L/min), α is the model-specific cortisol elimination rate constant (min^{-1}), and F_S is the steady state concentration of cortisol (nmol/L). Note that the term F_S in Equation 5 represents the concentration of total cortisol (X_{TotF}) in Model 1 and free cortisol (X_F) in Models 2-4 (see Supplementary Data, Section D, below).

Steady state equations for Models 1-4: Steady state equations may be obtained by setting the derivatives for change in cortisol concentration per time (in all compartments) equal to zero, as previously described (3,11). The dynamical equations for Models 1-4 are all simplified at steady state, as shown by steady state equations for Models 1-4 below:

Model 1: $Z_{\text{TotF}} = \alpha_1 * X_{\text{TotFS}}$, where X_{TotFS} is the steady state concentration of plasma total cortisol (X_{TotF}).

Model 2: $Z_F = \alpha_2 * X_{FS}$, where X_{FS} is the steady state concentration of plasma free cortisol
(X_F).

Model 3: $Z_F = \alpha_3 * X_{FS}$, where X_{FS} is the steady state concentration of plasma free cortisol
(X_F).

Model 4: $Z_F = \alpha_4 * X_{FS}$, where X_{FS} is the steady state concentration of plasma free cortisol
(X_F).

Although steady-state equations for Models 1-4 above all share the same functional form, they yield different solutions for steady state cortisol concentrations since the values for α are different for each model. Also note in comparing the dynamic equations (Eq 1-4 in manuscript) and steady state equation for Model 4 (above), this theorem includes the view that the permeability parameter (k) and extravascular volume (V_e) are not part of the steady state equation. Note as well that extravascular volume (V_e) is not considered in either dynamic or steady state formulations of Models 1-3.

Comment: For the same cortisol appearance rate (Z_F) expressed in units of concentration/time (nmol/L/min), the different elimination rate constants in Models 2-4 (α_{2-4}) predict different steady state concentrations of free cortisol (X_{FS}). At most, only one of these model-dependent elimination rate constants (α) can be expected to match experimental results (12).

Steady state solutions for cortisol elimination rates (α_{1-4}) for Models 1-4: Since the forms of Models 1-4 are similar only at steady state, this condition is useful for comparisons of α between models having different mathematical forms for their dynamic solution. Direct comparisons between α_{2-4} at steady state may be considered, since Models 2-4 consider the elimination of free cortisol (X_F). However, because the monoexponential elimination rate constant for Model 1

refers to total (X_{TotF}) rather than free (X_{F}) cortisol concentrations, comparisons of α_1 with α_2 - α_4 are indirect insofar as the relationship between steady state concentrations of total (X_{TotF}) and free (X_{F}) cortisol is non-linear.

H. Inverse transformation (one of the Box-Cox transformations) of cortisol elimination rate constant (α) to obtain cortisol half-life (τ): Reciprocal (harmonic) means are often used for the comparison of rates. In the case of the concentration-dependent cortisol elimination rate (α), the inverse transformation, shown by the formula $\tau = \ln(2)/\alpha$, was selected among the Box-Cox family of transformations in order to stabilize variances and linearize mean values (data not shown). Defining τ as the inverse function ($\ln(2)/\alpha$) means that we are using the same transformation of α in all four models. This approach was applied for some comparisons of elimination rates, including ordering of model-specific α solutions by their corresponding half-lives (τ_{1-4}) (see Section M, below). Also note that the term *half-life* typically implies the time for cortisol concentrations to decline to 50% of the initial value. This meaning of is explicit in the formulation of cortisol half-life in one-compartment models (τ_1 in Model 1 and τ_2 in Model 2). It is understood from the forgoing discussion of α_3 and α_4 , half-life solutions for multicompartment Models 3 and 4 (τ_3 and τ_4), as defined by the inverse transformation ($\tau = \ln(2)/\alpha$), explicitly do *not* reflect the time for initial cortisol concentrations to decrease by 50%.

I. Computation of the equilibrium disassociation constant (K_D) for binding of cortisol and CBG: Serum concentrations of CBG and total and free cortisol in CBG-deficient subjects homozygous for Gly237Val substitution in the CBG (SERPINA6) gene as well as *in vitro* cortisol binding studies of the mutant CBG protein have been previously reported (13). CBG-deficient subjects have abnormally low CBG concentrations (X_{TotCBG}) by definition and, compared to wild type CBG protein, the mutant CBG protein has markedly decreased cortisol

binding affinity (higher equilibrium dissociation constant K_D). The computation of K_D for cortisol and CBG binding is here based on multiple, paired measurements of free cortisol concentrations (X_F) and total cortisol concentration (X_{TotF}), as reported in Perogamvros *et al* (8), and their equilibrium relationship. The equilibrium can be seen by setting the left-hand side of differential equations 2) and 3) (in manuscript) equal to zero. These equilibria take place in considerably less than a second *in vitro*, as previously described (14). Note that all measurements of X_F and X_{TotF} in test tubes (at 37°C) are under these equilibrium conditions.

These equilibrium conditions yield $X_A = \frac{X_{TotA} * X_F}{K_A + X_F}$ and

$$X_C = \frac{X_{TotCBG} * X_F}{K_C + X_F}, \text{ where } K_A = \frac{\kappa_{-1}^A}{\kappa_1^A} \text{ and } K_C = \frac{\kappa_{-1}^C}{\kappa_1^C} \text{ are the equilibrium dissociation}$$

constants for free cortisol binding to albumin and CBG, respectively. Thus X_F is obtained from $X_{TotF} = X_F + X_C + X_A$ as a cubic equation solution and is a function of X_{TotF} which involves X_{TotA} , K_A , X_{TotCBG} and K_C in the coefficients (14). Here, population values for X_{TotA} were taken from the literature (9), X_{TotCBG} was measured, and K_C and K_A were estimated simultaneously by nonlinear least squares methods using the 15x2 points of measured pairs (X_F , X_{TotF}) for our two CBG-deficient subjects. These procedures yielded group average K_C of 124.4 nmol/L in the CBG-deficient group; K_C of 24.7 was similarly obtained in HV, which was consistent with binding studies of wild-type CBG reported for healthy controls (15,16). As Perogamvros *et al* did not detect appreciable cortisol binding activity for the mutant CBG protein *in vitro* (13), we consider our computed K_C (124.4 nmol/L) as an *effective* value.

J. Model 4 simulations: We performed simulations to illustrate dynamic behaviors of Model 4 solutions for both bolus and continuous infusion experiments. These behaviors point to the fact that Model 4 is realistic insofar as it reproduces experimental results reported in the

literature (5,12,17). Simulations for bolus and continuous infusion experiments assumed an initial cortisol concentration of zero with infusion into the vascular compartment (V) at a defined rate (mass/time). These simulations replicated experimental conditions, for example 15, 20, and 25 mg over 20 seconds for the bolus experiment (5,8) and 8 mg/h for the continuous infusion experiment (12), thus facilitating comparisons with previously published experimental data. Mean values for Model 4 parameters obtained in the HV group were used for the simulations (Table 2). Simulations for group comparisons (HV vs. CBG-deficient) used mean HV values for α_4 and k and group-specific values for CBG concentration, CBG-cortisol binding affinity, V, and V_e (Table 2).

We were also interested in examining whether the physiology, defined by Model 4 equations, could explain anomalous observations in the literature obtained using Models 1-3. For example, Arafah observed significantly longer cortisol half-life (τ_1) for 25 compared to 15 mg hydrocortisone bolus dose (5). That finding is anomalous, since one might suppose cortisol half-life (and elimination rate) to be an intrinsic property of individual subjects that might vary between subjects but would not be expected to systematically vary according to bolus dose. To address this issue, cortisol concentration data were generated *in silico* using Model 4; previously used models having lower levels of complexity (Models 1-3) were then fit to these data to see if anomalous experimental observations were replicated. This approach was applied for different hydrocortisone bolus doses (15 vs. 25 mg) and shown in Figure S5 below (Supplementary Data, Section T).

A similar approach was used in *post-hoc* analysis of the significant model-group interaction (see Results, Table 2) observed in our comparison of HV and CBG-deficient groups (illustrated in Figure 4 in the manuscript).

L. Generalization of model-specific elimination rates obtained from the bolus

experiment (α_1 - α_4) to the continuous infusion experiment (simulation): Both the bolus and continuous infusion experiments have inputs of mass/time (nmol/min) directly into the vascular volume (V). The vascular volume is reasonably well defined in the literature (10). Beyond this, V for both bolus and continuous infusion experiments should be the same for any given individual subject. Using the experimentally determined rate of cortisol infusion used in Prete *et al* (12) (8 mg/h \approx 368 nmol/min) and applying normative values for vascular volume, one can compute model-specific time to steady state and steady state concentrations of cortisol using the values of α determined in the bolus experiment, as previously described (11). These comparisons of model-predicted and experimentally determined measures (time to steady state and steady state cortisol concentrations) were used as performance measure of generalizability of model-specific parameters between the bolus and continuous hydrocortisone infusion experiments. When Models 1-4 are applied to simulation of the continuous infusion experiment, they all predict an asymptotic approach to steady state cortisol concentrations. Time to steady state in these simulations was defined by the time needed to reach 95% of the model-predicted asymptotic cortisol concentrations ($X_{T_{0.95}}$ for Models 1,3, and 4, and X_F for Model 2), as shown in the manuscript (Figure 3 and continuous infusion simulations).

M. Ordered relationships of model-specific solutions for cortisol elimination rates (α) and

half-lives (τ): Mathematical arguments based on equations for Models 1-4 demonstrate that, when applied to the same set of cortisol concentration elimination data and assuming comparable conditions for CBG and albumin concentrations and their binding affinities, the following order

is consistently observed: $\alpha_1 > \alpha_2 > \alpha_3 > \alpha_4$ and $\tau_4 < \tau_3 < \tau_2 < \tau_1$ (data not shown). Note as well that equations for Models 1-4 are ordered by complexity:

$$\{\text{Model 1} \approx \text{Model 2}\} < \text{Model 3} < \text{Model 4}.$$

Differential equations governing Models 1-4 (assuming no input $Z(t)=0$) are shown in Eq 1-4), respectively:

$$\text{Model 1) } \frac{d \text{Tot}F}{dt} = -\alpha_1 \text{Tot}F$$

$$\text{Model 2) } \frac{d F}{dt} = -\alpha_2 F$$

$$\text{Model 3) } \frac{d \text{Tot}F}{dt} = -\alpha_3 F$$

$$\text{Model 4) } \frac{d \text{Tot}F}{dt} = -\alpha_4 F - \frac{k}{V_e} (F - F_e) \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{d F_e}{dt} = + \frac{k}{V_e} (F - F_e)$$

Herein, we demonstrate that pair-wise comparisons will show that for the same set of cortisol concentration data, half-lives are systematically ordered ($\alpha_1 < \alpha_2 < \alpha_3$); subsequently, we show that $\alpha_3 < \alpha_4$.

To compare the half-lives given by Models 1-3, we note the definition of r = fraction that free cortisol (X_F) is of the total cortisol ($X_{\text{Tot}F}$) satisfies $F = r * \text{Tot}F$; r may also be reported as free cortisol (X_F) as a % of total cortisol ($X_{\text{Tot}F}$).

Before more valid arguments are given, we give one faulty argument.

Claim. If r were constant, then $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2$.

Multiplying equation *Model 2*) by r yields $\frac{d r * F}{dt} = -\alpha_2 r * F$ which is $\frac{d \text{Tot}F}{dt} = -\alpha_2 \text{Tot}F$,

and compared to equation 1 gives $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2$ (or $\tau_1 = \tau_2$).

Comment. However, r is not a constant and the Claim is vacuous. This argument relies on

the comparison of differential equations. We don't know if there is a calculus for comparison of differential equations. Thus, the approach taken here relies on comparison of functions (solutions) rather than on the comparison of differential equations.

To be clearer, we solve our 3 differential equations for Models 1-3 to obtain

Model 1') $TotF = TotF_0 e^{-\alpha_1 t}$, rewritten as $TotF = r_0 F_0 * e^{-\alpha_1 t}$, and

Model 2') $F = F_0 e^{-\alpha_2 t}$, rewritten as $TotF = r(t) * F_0 * e^{-\alpha_2 t}$, and

Model 3') $TotF = TotF_0 * \exp \left\{ -\alpha_3 \int_0^t r(\tau) d\tau \right\}$ rewritten as $TotF = r_0 F_0 * \exp \left\{ -\alpha_3 \int_0^t r(\tau) d\tau \right\}$.

We obtain Equation 3 by rewriting the term $\alpha_3 F$ as $\alpha_3 r(t) TotF$ and by the standard method of solving a differential equation using an integrating factor (18).

Similar methods lead to solution 4) for Model 4):

$$Model\ 4')\ TotF(t) = \frac{k}{V} \int_0^t \exp \left\{ -\left(\alpha_4 + \frac{k}{V} \right) \int_{\tau}^t r(x) dx \right\} F_e(\tau) d\tau .\ where$$

$$F_e(t) = \int_0^t \frac{k}{V_e} \exp \left\{ -\frac{k}{V_e} (t - \tau) \right\} F(\tau) d\tau$$

Comments.

1. In Model 4'), $F_e(t)$ is a convolution integral of $F(t)$ with an exponential probability density function (pdf) and as such F_e is a smoothed and delayed version of free cortisol function $F(t)$ with mean delay is $\frac{V_e}{k}$ minutes. Smoothing is the result of integration.
2. In Model 4'), the *bona fide* convolution integral for $F_e(t)$, the parameter k/V_e must appear in two places—in the exponent, and as a multiplier. Referring back to the differential equations that gave rise to this convolution, one must have k/V_e in two places—as a coefficient of $F_e(t)$ and as a multiplier of $F(t)$. For example, if the coefficient were k_1/V_e and the multiplier were k_2/V_e , then the second parameter could be replaced by $\frac{k_2}{k_1} * k_1/V_e$

in order to obtain $\frac{k_2}{k_1} * \int_0^t \frac{k_1}{V_e} \exp\left\{-\frac{k_1}{V_e}(t-\tau)\right\} F(\tau) d\tau$, which is not a *bona fide* convolution integral of Fick's law owing to the multiplier $\left(\frac{k_2}{k_1}\right)$.

3. In fact, there is probability formulation where the convolution integral can be represented by the sum of independent random variables. Thus, the delay is an exponential distributed random variable with mean $\frac{V_e}{k}$. Note that the transform to the space of random variables is analogous to Laplace transforms. In turn, TotF(t) is like a convolution integral if we transform time by the mapping function.

$$T = \int_0^t r(x) dx \text{ so that } \int_{\tau}^t r(x) dx = T(t) - T(\tau) \approx r(t)(t - \tau).$$

Since we intend to compare exponents of the first 3 solutions, let us list them here.

Model 1'') $-\alpha_1 t + \ln(r_0)$; and

Model 2'') $-\alpha_2 t + \ln(r(t))$; and

Model 3'') $-\alpha_3 \int_0^t r(\tau) d\tau + \ln(r_0)$, where $\int_0^t r(\tau) d\tau < \int_0^t 1 d\tau = t$ since $r < 1$.

We will need to know more about $r(t)$ (where $100*r(t) = \% \text{ of } X_F \text{ out of } X_{\text{TotF}}$).

Proposition 1. In the elimination model with no input secretion, $r(t)$ is a decreasing function of t .

Justification. We use the equilibrium cubic equation derived elsewhere (14), which can be written as

$$3) \text{ TotF} = F + F * \frac{\text{TotC}}{K_C + F} + F * \frac{\text{TotA}}{K_A + F}, \text{ where TotC= total CBG, TotA= total Albumin,}$$

and K_C, K_A are the corresponding equilibrium disassociation constants for cortisol binding to CBG and albumin, respectively.

Equation 3 implies TotF is increasing if and only if F is.

Further, $r(t) = F/\text{TotF} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\text{TotC}}{K_C + F} + \frac{\text{TotA}}{K_A + F}}$ implies $r(t)$ is decreasing if and only if F is.

Clearly TotF must be a decreasing function of t (elimination with no input); $r(t)$ is also.

Comment. It is true that this is not at equilibrium, but we know equilibrium takes place rapidly (14). In fact, all measurements done from test tube samples will be at equilibrium.

Proposition 2. Half life τ_1 is greater than τ_2 .

Justification. Suppose equations 1' and 2' are fit in the same experiment to the same TotF vs t data. Thereby, these two functions are approximately equal. Comparing exponents, we obtain

$-\alpha_1 t + \ln(r_0) \approx -\alpha_2 t + \ln(r(t))$ or $(\alpha_2 - \alpha_1) t \approx \ln(r(t)) - \ln(r_0) < 0$, since $r(t) < r_0$ by proposition 1. This implies $(\alpha_2 - \alpha_1)$ must be negative; that is, $\alpha_2 < \alpha_1$.

Finally $t_2 > t_1$ since $t = \ln(2)/\alpha$.

Proposition 3. $t_2 > t_3$.

Justification. Suppose equations Model 2) and Model 3) are fit in the same experiment to the same TotF vs t data. Thereby, these two functions are approximately equal. Comparing exponents in Model 2') and Model 3'), we obtain

$-\alpha_2 t + \ln(r(t)) \approx -\alpha_3 \int_0^t r(\tau) d\tau + \ln(r_0)$ or $(\alpha_3 \int_0^t r(\tau) d\tau - \alpha_2 t) \approx \ln(r_0) - \ln(r(t)) > 0$.

by proposition 1. Now $(\alpha_3 t - \alpha_2 t) > (\alpha_3 \int_0^t r(\tau) d\tau - \alpha_2 t) > 0$, since $\int_0^t r(\tau) d\tau < \int_0^t 1 d\tau = t$ and $r(t) < 1$. So $(\alpha_3 - \alpha_2) > 0$ that is, $\alpha_3 > \alpha_2$. Finally $t_3 < t_2$ since $t = \ln(2)/\alpha$.

Combining propositions, we have

Proposition. $\tau_1 > \tau_2 > \tau_3$.

The mathematical comparison of τ_3 and τ_4 is to be determined. However, using Monte Carlo simulations to generate cortisol concentration elimination data (19), the ordered sequence of solutions $\tau_3 > \tau_4$ was consistently observed (data not shown).

Comments:

1. Note that Models 2-4 are nested. For example, if one sets $k=0$ in Model 4, it becomes

Model 3. Similarly, if the binding affinities for CBG and albumin are set to zero in Model 3, it becomes Model 2. However, Model 1 is not nested in Model 2 though comparing the solutions 1') and 2') above we see that Model 1 is a restriction of Model 2 by setting $r(t)$ equal to $r(0) = r_0$. In other words, one can assume for Model 1 that the X_F as a percent of X_{TotF} is constant. These justifications are not proofs. For example, two functions are approximately equal is ill-defined here.

N. Correlation between model-specific solutions for cortisol elimination rate constant (α_{1-4}) obtained from the bolus experiment (Table S1): As shown in Table S1, the cortisol elimination rate constant for Model 4 (α_4) was not significantly correlated with α_{1-3} , whereas α_1 – α_3 were all significantly and positively correlated with one another.

Supplementary Data Table S1					
Correlations between model-dependent estimates for α					
Model		1	2	3	4
	Model-specific cortisol elimination rate constant (α)	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4
1	α_1		r=0.98, P<0.001	r=0.84, P=0.03	NS r=0.19, P=0.72
2	α_2			r=0.90, P=0.01	NS r=0.28, P=0.6
3	α_3				NS r=0.48, P=0.33

O. Optimized solutions for Models 1-4 for a representative, HV subject (Figure S1):

Figure S1. Measured vs. model-predicted serum cortisol concentrations for Models 1-4 for a representative HV subject. Solutions were optimized by least squared errors for Models 1-4. Optimized solutions for measured (open circles) and model-predicted total (X_{TotF} , solid lines) or free (X_{F} , dashed line) are shown for an individual, representative HV subject. Also shown are corresponding goodness of fit summary measures (bias, standard deviation, and root mean squared error).

P. Interaction of hydrocortisone bolus dose and CBG and albumin concentration on time to intersection point (T^*) (hydrocortisone bolus experiment) (Figures S2):

Figure S2. Interaction of hydrocortisone bolus dose (x-axis) and CBG and albumin concentrations on time to intersection point (T^*) (y-axis) *in silico*. Time T^* (min) of intersection (Fe^*) for two levels each of total CBG and albumin concentrations. T^* vs. dose for $X_{TotCBG}=451$ and $X_{TotA}=331,000$ nM (blue); $X_{TotCBG}=451$ and $X_{TotA}=662,000$ nM (red); $X_{TotCBG}=901$ and $X_{TotA}=331,000$ nM (green); and $X_{TotCBG}=901$ and $X_{TotA}=662,000$ nM (purple).

Q. Effects of plasma volume (V) on maximal extravascular cortisol concentration (X_{Fe^*}) and Model 3 solutions for τ_3 (20 mg bolus simulation) (Figure S3): In this simulation, cortisol concentrations were generated *in silico* using Model 4. Values for all parameters (Table 2,

Model 4, HV) with the exception of plasma volume (V) were held constant. As shown in Figure S3, plasma volume (V) was negatively correlated with X_{Fe^*} .

Figure S3: Maximal extravascular cortisol concentration (X_{Fe^*}) as a function of vascular volume (V). The time to intersection point, T^* , was also positively correlated with V and varied from 7.4-9.4 minutes over the range of plasma volumes (V) plotted in Figure S2 (data not shown). As a consequence of the attenuated rate of decline in plasma cortisol concentrations after T^* , half-life solutions obtained by Models 1-3 (τ_{1-3}) were all positively correlated with V in this simulation (data not shown). In the case of Model 3 solutions, both the lower plasma volumes as well as lower concentrations and lower affinity of CBG in the CBG-deficient group contributed to higher X_{Fe^*} relative to HV, thus explaining our finding of longer τ_3 in CBG-deficient relative to HV in Table 2 in the manuscript.

R. Simulation analysis of the relationship of Model 1 solutions for cortisol half-life (τ_1) to CBG concentration (Figure S4): Cortisol concentrations were generated *in silico* using identical values for all parameters (Table 2, Model 4, HV) other than CBG concentration (X_{TotCBG}). Solutions for τ_1 were obtained by applying Model 1 to the computer-generated cortisol concentrations. As shown in Figure S4, τ_1 was positively correlated with CBG concentration. CBG-cortisol binding affinity had similar effects on Model solutions for cortisol half-life (τ_1),

which was demonstrated by negative correlation of τ_1 on CBG equilibrium dissociation constant (K_C) (data not shown).

Figure S4. Total plasma cortisol concentrations were generated in silico for standard conditions (20 mg bolus, mean HV albumin concentrations and parameter solutions (Table 2), while CBG concentration was varied. Model 1 was applied to cortisol concentrations to obtain half-life estimates (τ_1).

S. Three sources of systematic modeling errors (diffusion, protein binding, and elimination errors) identified by pairwise model comparisons (Table S2): In the following discussion, we treat the pairwise difference between adjacent models (Model 1 vs. Model 2 vs. Model 3 vs. Model 4) as sources of error in relation to omission or distortion of specific terms present in the more complete system of equations represented by Model 4 (see

Eq 1-4, Methods section in manuscript). As there are four models and three pairwise comparisons of adjacent models, three distinct types of error may be ascertained. Also, the main effects of our three types of errors are pairwise *differences* of adjacent half-lives. For example, $\tau_3-\tau_4$ is the main effect for diffusion errors, $\tau_2-\tau_3$ is the main effect for mass action errors, and $\tau_2-\tau_1$ is the main effect for elimination errors (see Table S2).

The first source of error, *diffusion error*, is related to omission of the terms beginning with $-k/V$ (Eq 1) and k/V_e (Eq 4). These terms for cortisol diffusion are absent in Model 3 equations (see above). A second source of error, *protein binding error*, is illustrated by the difference between Model 3 and Model 2 and related to omission of protein-binding equations for saturable cortisol binding to CBG (Eq 2) and albumin (Eq 3). A third source of error, *elimination error*, is related to the cortisol elimination rate constant (α), as represented in Eq 1 for example. Elimination error may be illustrated by the difference between Model 2, and Model 1 solutions for cortisol elimination rates. Whereas Model 2 accounts for the elimination of free cortisol (X_F), this relationship is distorted in Model 1, which applies the monoexponential elimination process to total cortisol (X_{TotF}). Thus, Models 1-3 are affected by diffusion error, Models 1-2 are affected by protein binding error, and Model 1 is affected by elimination error (see Supplementary Data Table S2) in comparison to Model 4. Whereas Model 3 is only affected by diffusion error, errors are compounded to greater or lesser extent in Models 1 and 2, respectively. In addition, there are effects of variation in physiological parameters, e.g. CBG and albumin concentrations, vascular and extravascular volumes, etc.) that differentially interact with above errors (see Figures S2-S4, above).

Only Model 1 was affected by elimination error, which had a relatively large impact on Model 1 half-life solutions (τ_1) and demonstrated significant negative interaction with CBG-deficient condition, as illustrated in Figure 5 and summarized in Supplementary Data Table S2. Interaction between elimination error and CBG concentrations is the likely explanation for the positive correlation between CBG concentration and τ_1 observed in previous studies (8,20). Half-life estimates for other protein bound hormones, such as testosterone and vitamin

Supplementary Data Table S2. Expression of model differences as sources of error in relation to Eq 1-4 (diffusion, protein binding, and elimination errors)

Source of error	Pairwise model comparison isolating error effects	Term(s) from Eq 1-4 missing from less complex model (Models 1-3)	Effect on the difference of half-lives (τ) in CBG-deficient (compared to HV)*	Model solution(s) affected by error
Diffusion error	Model 3 vs. Model 4 ($\tau_3-\tau_4$)	Cortisol flux (diffusion) Eq 1 (circled term, $V \rightarrow V_e$) and Eq 4 ($V_e \rightarrow V$)	$(\tau_3-\tau_4) \uparrow\uparrow$	Models 1-3
Protein binding error	Model 2 vs. Model 3 ($\tau_2-\tau_3$)	Mass action equations for cortisol binding to CBG (Eq 2) and albumin (Eq 3)	$(\tau_2-\tau_3) \downarrow$	Models 1- 2
Elimination error	Model 1 vs. Model 2 ($\tau_1-\tau_2$)	α term in equation 1 (applies to total rather than free cortisol elimination)	$(\tau_1-\tau_2) \downarrow\downarrow\downarrow$	Model 1

*Effects listed in column 4 are for positive differences in half-lives (τ) owing to ordered half-lives by model complexity ($\tau_4 < \tau_3 < \tau_2 < \tau_1$) and the arrows indicate the sign and magnitude of the sources of errors in CBG- deficient compared to HV. Also see Table 2 (in manuscript).

D metabolites, have been derived using disposition models analogous to Model 1, and may also be subject to similar elimination error interactions related to concentration and/or affinity of cognate serum binding protein(s) (21). Diffusion error affected solutions for Models 1-3 and also interacts significantly with a variety of factors, including vascular volume, baseline

free cortisol concentration, hydrocortisone dose, and CBG concentration (Figure S2 and S3, Table S2, and data not shown).

T. *In silico* study replicating dose-dependent variation in τ_1 (15 vs. 25 mg hydrocortisone bolus dose) (Figure S5): In healthy, DEX-suppressed subjects, Arafah estimated *terminal* total cortisol half-life (τ_1) by applying Model 1 to plasma total cortisol concentrations measured at specified intervals 60-360 min after iv bolus hydrocortisone (15 vs. 25 mg) (5). His finding of significantly longer terminal cortisol half-life for the 25 mg ($\tau_1 = 121.2 \pm 9$ min) compared to 15 mg ($\tau_1 = 108.6 \pm 6.6$ min) dose (5) is consistent with dose-dependent variation in apparent total cortisol half-life (τ_1) reported in previous studies (23,24). As illustrated in Figure S5, Model 4 predicts a longer intersection time (T^*) and lower maximal extravascular cortisol concentration (X_{Fe}^*) for the 15 mg (Panel A) compared to 25 mg (Panel B) bolus simulations. The higher X_{Fe}^* for the 25 mg dose was associated with a higher rate of extravascular to vascular cortisol flux after T^* , and consequently higher cortisol concentrations throughout the period after T^* . Since Model 1 considers monoexponential elimination of total cortisol from a single compartment, Model 1 solutions may be conveniently plotted for X_{TotF} in log-transformed space. Panel C demonstrates the modest, dose-dependent differences in slopes, which correspond to half-lives of ≈ 106 and 115 min for 15 mg and 25 mg doses, respectively. Thus, *in silico* simulations closely approximated experimental results of Arafah (5). A similar mechanism involving higher X_{Fe}^* appeared to account for sequence-dependent effects (longer τ_1 for the same bolus dose given 6 h after an initial dose) observed in Arafah (5) (data not shown).

Figure S5: Simulation for 15 mg and 25 mg bolus dose replicating experimental data of Arafah. Model-predicted plasma free cortisol (blue, open circle) and extravascular free cortisol (X_{Fe} , red, open triangles) for 15 mg (Panel A) and 25 mg (Panel B) bolus doses. Note the higher X_{Fe}^* and earlier T^* for the larger (25 mg) bolus. Panel C shows natural logarithm of X_{TotF} response as a function of time (minutes) for 15 mg bolus ($\ln(X_{TotF})$, which yielded τ_1 of 100 min (blue regression line and circles) and for 25 mg bolus ($\ln(X_{TotF})$, which yielded τ_1 of 107 min (red regression line and circles).

U. Role of model artifact (transposition error) in the anomalous finding of significantly

decreased CSR in ECI vs. controls (25): As demonstrated in Sections C and M above, parameter solutions such as cortisol elimination rate (α) and half-life (τ) are contextual (model-specific). Therefore, it is not feasible to transpose absolute values or relative differences in τ (or α) from one model to another. In the example of Boonen *et al* (25), Model 3 was applied to cortisol concentrations measured in control and ECI groups. They reported the anomalous finding that CSR was significantly *reduced* in ECI relative to controls (25), whereas other studies demonstrated significantly increased CSR in ECI relative to controls (3,6,26). The perspective provided by our exposition of Model 4 equations and model comparisons suggests that this finding was due to model artifact (*transposition error*). In particular, Boonen *et al* applied the (mean) 7-fold difference in τ_1 (controls vs. ECI) obtained using Model 1 in association with 100 mg hydrocortisone bolus (6) to τ_3 in Model 3 solutions for endogenous cortisol secretion rates (25). That this finding was driven by transposition artifact was also supported by the observed difference in *goodness of fit* (model-predicted vs. measured cortisol concentrations) in ECI vs. controls in Boonen *et al* (25). Whereas Model 3 provided a good fit to measured cortisol concentrations in controls, in whom τ_3 was optimized using numerical methods, a poor fit was observed in ECI subjects in whom an artificially extended τ_3 (7-fold longer τ_3 than controls) was imposed on solutions for CSR. In particular, the observed rate of decline of X_{TotF} in ECI was far more rapid than model-predicted solutions,

confirming that the assignment imposition of 7-fold longer τ_3 was unrealistic. These observations also highlight the interdependence of elimination and appearance rate solutions inherent in numerical methods and the potential hazards of incorrect selection/assignment of key parameter values (2,27).

V. Limitations of the stable isotope dilution method. The stable isotope dilution has been considered a *gold standard* method for measurement of endogenous rates of cortisol appearance. However, the perspective provided in exposition of Model 4 equations raise several areas of concern for the accuracy of the method, particularly in its contemporary applications that consider X_{TotF} as a single compartment (Model 1) and include a bolus (priming) dose at the initiation of continuous D4-cortisol infusion. In addition, critical illness is associated with several physiologic adaptations, including (i) decreased concentrations of CBG, free CBG (X_{freeCBG}), and albumin, (ii) increased X_{F} , and (iii) increased X_{F} expressed as a percent of X_{TotF} . The physiologic adaptations may further complicate the determination of endogenous cortisol appearance rates by stable isotope dilution methods and comparisons between control and critically ill groups.

Implicit in the use of the ratio of $X_{\text{TotF}}/X_{\text{D4-TotF}}$ as the factor by which the known rate of D4-cortisol infusion (mass/time) is multiplied to calculate endogenous cortisol secretion rate is the assumption that a proportional relationship obtains between X_{TotF} and endogenous cortisol appearance rates (Z_{QTotF}). Similarly, the stable isotope method also assumes that plasma concentrations of total D4-cortisol ($X_{\text{D4-TotF}}$) are linearly related to D4-cortisol infusion rate. The method also assumes proportionality between labeled and unlabeled cortisol appearance rates and concentrations, viz. $Z_{\text{TotF}}/Z_{\text{D4-TotF}} = X_{\text{TotF}}/X_{\text{D4-TotF}}$. However, these proportionate

relationships are only applicable if *both* endogenous cortisol and D4-cortisol are at steady state.

Boonen *et al* (6) as a contemporary example of the stable isotope dilution used in conjunction with bolus (priming) dose of D4-cortisol and Model 1 assumptions: We refer to the seminal paper of Boonen *et al* as an important example of contemporary use of stable isotope dilution methods to measure rates of endogenous cortisol appearance (dQ_{TotF}/dt) (6). In the stable isotope component of that study, 11 patients (ECI) and 9 controls were given a 0.7 mg bolus of D4-cortisol, followed by a continuous infusion of D4-cortisol at a rate of 0.35 mg/h. 64% of the patients had systematic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS). Four plasma samples were drawn at 5 min intervals from 160-180 min post bolus/infusion, and mean values of the four samples were used to determine the ratio of $X_{\text{TotF}}/X_{\text{D4-TotF}}$ by subject. The mean value for $X_{\text{TotF}}/X_{\text{D4-TotF}}$ for each subject was multiplied by the infusion rate of D4-cortisol (0.35 mg/h) to obtain the appearance rate of endogenous cortisol, expressed in units of mass/time (dQ/dt) (6). During the period of continuous D4-cortisol infusion (0-180 min), a bolus (priming) dose of D2-cortisone (0.08 mg) was administered at 100 min, at which time continuous infusion of D2-cortisone was initiated at rate of 0.1053 mg/h. Note that cortisone binds CBG, but with reduced affinity relative to cortisol (15). Boonen *et al* observed that relative to controls, patients had significantly higher concentrations of D4-cortisol ($X_{\text{D4-TotF}}$). In addition, endogenous total plasma cortisol concentrations (X_{TotF}) were significantly (3.5-fold) higher in patients than controls. Rates of endogenous cortisol appearance (dQ_{TotF}/dt) were also significantly higher in patients than controls. In the ECI group, rates of cortisol appearance were significantly higher in patients with SIRS (3.4 ± 1.1 mg/h) than those who did not have the syndrome (1.8 ± 1.1 mg/h); cortisol appearance rate was $\approx 1.5 \pm 1.8$ in controls. The authors

report that D4-cortisol concentrations were at steady state by 60 min. However, that premise was not rigorously tested by analysis of repeated measures. In fact, it appears that mean concentrations of D4-cortisol were decreasing during the infusion period in both patients and controls. In controls, X_{TotF} also appeared to significantly decrease during the D4-cortisol infusion period (1000-1300 h).

Questions raised by Model 4 equations concerning the reliability of contemporary application of stable isotope methods to estimate rates of endogenous cortisol

appearance: The development of Model 4 equations and model comparisons provide additional perspectives on the use of stable isotope methods to measure cortisol appearance rates. These includes perspectives on (i) steady state (see Section H), (ii) competition of D4-cortisol and endogenous cortisol for saturable binding sites on CBG, (iii) potential impact of bolus (priming) dose of D4-cortisol, (iv) interdependence of endogenous and D4-cortisol concentrations with respect to protein-binding, elimination, GR binding, and diffusion coefficient, but independence of endogenous and D4-cortisol with respect to rates of transcompartmental cortisol flux due to differences in free cortisol concentration gradients ($X_F - X_{Fe}$) vs. ($X_{D4-F} - X_{D4Fe}$), and (v) feedback inhibition of endogenous cortisol secretion mediated by D4-cortisol infusion.

1. **Steady state only obtains when all cortisol compartments are at steady state:** Model 4 equations reinforce the principle that steady state conditions obtain only when all cortisol compartments are in steady state. For endogenous cortisol, that implies that X_F , X_C , X_A , and X_{Fe} are all approximately constant. However, endogenous cortisol secretion is pulsatile in nature ($dZ_F/dt \neq 0$), and there is evidence that endogenous cortisol secretion is also pulsatile in the setting of critical illness.

For exogenous D4-cortisol as well, steady state conditions obtain only if D4-cortisol concentrations in all four compartments, namely free (X_{D4-F}), CBG-bound (X_{D4-C}), albumin-bound (X_{D4-A}), and extravascular (X_{D4-Fe}) D4-cortisol are approximately constant. However, because both endogenous and D4-cortisol compete for binding to limited concentrations of free CBG (15,28), we recognize that non-steady conditions for endogenous cortisol also disrupt the steady state for D4-cortisol. Therefore, steady state conditions for the continuous infusion of D4-cortisol require that cortisol concentrations in all four compartments for *both* endogenous and D4-labeled cortisol are approximately constant. As well, we recognize that the D2-cortisone, which was administered as a priming bolus (0.08 mg) at 100 min followed by continuous infusion D2-cortisone, also competes with endogenous and D4-cortisol for CBG binding (15). Therefore, the steady state condition requires, in addition to above restrictions, that derivative of D2-cortisol concentrations in all four compartments is also approximately zero (28).

2. **Under non-steady state conditions, transcompartmental cortisol flux complicates the relationship between cortisol appearance rate and X_{TotF} :** Model 4 equations indicate that at steady state $X_F \approx X_{Fe}$, net transcompartmental cortisol flux is zero, and the distribution volume relevant to steady state conditions is restricted to the plasma volume (V). By contrast, under non-steady state conditions, $X_F \neq X_{Fe}$, net transcompartmental cortisol flux is ongoing at time-varying rates ($dQ/dt \neq 0$), and the distribution volumes include not only vascular (V) but also extravascular (V_e). Accordingly, depending on the phase of endogenous cortisol pulses, higher (or lower) rates of cortisol appearance may be necessary to achieve a given concentration of cortisol under non-steady state conditions when compared to steady state.

3. **Approximately constant concentrations of $X_{D4-TotF}$ may not be a reliable indicator of**

steady state conditions: It also follows from the above discussion as well as the substantial time lag between X_F and X_{Fe} (Figure 3), that $X_{D4-TotF}$ may appear to be relatively constant even though steady state conditions do not obtain.

4. **Rates of endogenous and D4-cortisol flux are determined by their respective concentration gradients, complicating the assumption that their respective dispositions *in vivo* are**

identical: An assumption of the stable isotope method is that the disposition of D4-cortisol is identical to that of endogenous cortisol, including its on- and off-rates for binding to CBG, albumin, and glucocorticoid receptor (GR), rate of elimination, etc. This assumption informs the principle that, since mixing in the vascular volume and equilibration among binding proteins is rapid, the free, CBG-bound, and albumin-bound cortisol expressed as fraction of X_{TotF} are the same as those ratios for labeled cortisol: $X_F/X_{TotF} = X_{D4-F}/X_{D4-TotF}$; $X_C/X_{TotF} = X_{D4-C}/X_{D4-TotF}$; $X_A/X_{TotF} = X_{D4-A}/X_{D4-TotF}$. However, these interdependent behaviors of endogenous and labeled cortisol do *not* apply to rates of diffusion. That is because the rate of diffusion for D4-cortisol depends on its concentration gradient ($X_{D4-F} - X_{D4-Fe}$), which is, apart from effects related to competition with endogenous cortisol for binding proteins, is otherwise *independent* of the concentration gradient related to endogenous cortisol ($X_F - X_{Fe}$). In other words, rates of transcompartmental flux of labeled and endogenous cortisol cannot be assumed to be identical under non-steady state conditions.

5. Influence of priming (bolus) doses of D4-cortisol (and D2-cortisone): Model 4 predictions suggest that the 0.7 mg bolus (priming) dose of D4-cortisol will reach T^* slowly (see Figure S2), and extravascular \rightarrow vascular flux of D4-cortisol will contribute to X_{TotF} for a protracted period of time after the priming bolus. Depending on the rate of continuous D4-cortisol infusion

and timing, contributions from extravascular→vascular flux of D4-cortisol, $X_{D4-TotF}$ may be still be declining from the bolus before steady state concentrations at a lower concentration of $X_{D4-TotF}$ has been reached. Such a phenomenon could, for example, explain the observation of decreasing concentrations of $X_{D4-TotF}$ in Boonen *et al* (6), and also raise the concern that steady state concentrations of $X_{D4-TotF}$ may be lower than those measured between 160-180 min.

6. Feedback effects mediated by D4-cortisol: The infusion of D4-cortisol at rates that produce substantial elevations in plasma concentrations may be associated with feedback inhibition of the HPA axis and decreased rates of endogenous cortisol secretion. For example, in the data of Boonen *et al*, concentrations of X_{TotF} decreased as a function of time during the infusion of D4-cortisol (6). While this decrease could be due to diurnal variation, it could also be related to feedback effects of D4-cortisol infusion. These feedback effects are likely to vary between ECI and control subjects (data not shown), further confounding between-group comparisons for cortisol appearance rates. between group.

Summary: The development of Model 4 equations raises several unanswered questions regarding the model assumptions and accuracy of the stable isotope method. These considerations are especially relevant in its contemporary applications, which include Model 1 assumptions (X_{TotF} as a single compartment), use of a priming (bolus) dose of D4-cortisol, and comparisons between groups (critical illness vs. healthy controls) that differ in characteristics such as CBG concentration and free cortisol concentrations. Therefore, additional evaluation is necessary before stable isotope dilution methods may be considered to be a *gold standard* or fully accurate method for measurement of endogenous cortisol appearance rates.

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